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ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ НАРУШЕНИЯХ МОЗГОВОГО КРОВООБРАЩЕНИЯ**<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834739>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В нашем наблюдении приняли участие 46 пациентов с когнитивными расстройствами (возраст 65-85 лет) в двух идентичных группах: 23 пациента в основной группе и 23 пациента во второй группе. Нами было использовано препарат MLC 601 (NeuroAIDII) для лечения нашей основной группы пациентов в течение 3 месяцев и анализировали эффективность второй группы пациентов при проведении традиционных медицинских процедур. После лечения эффективность была достоверно определена у пациентов основной группы по сравнению с пациентами второй группы.

Ключевые слова: когнитивные нарушения, препарат MLC 601 (NeuroAIDII).

Mirjuraev Elbek MirshavkatovichCenter for Development of Professional Qualification of Medical Workers
under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan**Samiev Asliddin Saitovich****Jiyanov Zafarjon Bokhodirovich**
Samarkand State Medical University**ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH COGNITIVE CHANGES IN CHRONIC
CEREBRAL CIRCULATION DISEASES****ANNOTATION**

A total of 46 patients with cognitive disorders (their age was 65-85 years old) participated in our observation in two identical groups: 23 patients in the main group and 23 patients in the second group. We used the drug MLC601 (NeuroAIDII) for the treatment of our main group of patients for 3 months, and we analyzed the effectiveness of the second group of patients by conducting traditional medical procedures. After treatment, efficacy was reliably determined in our main group patients compared to our second group patients.

Keywords: cognitive impairment, drug MLC601 (NeuroAIDII).

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Самарканд давлат тиббиёт университети**БОШ МИЯДА СУРУНКАЛИ КОН АЙЛАНИШИ КАСАЛЛАРИДАГИ КОГНИТИВ ЎЗГАРИШЛИ БЕМОЛЛАРИНИ
ДАВОЛАШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ ТАХЛИЛИ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Кузатувимизда жами 46 нафар когнитив бузулишли (уларнинг ёши 65-85 ёшни ташкил қилди) беморлар иккита бир хил гуруҳларга: асосий гуруҳни 23 нафар ва иккинчи гуруҳ-23 беморларимиз иштирок этди. Асосий гуруҳ беморларимизга MLC601 (NeuroAIDII) препаратини 3 ой давомида даволаш мақсадида қўлладик, иккинчи гуруҳ беморларимизга эса ананавий даво муолажаларини олиб бориш йўли билан улардаги самарадорлик кўрсаткичини тахлил қилдик. Даволашдан кейин асосий гуруҳ беморларимизда иккинчи гуруҳ беморларимизга нисбатан ишончли тарзда самарадорлик аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: когнитив бузулишлар, MLC601 (NeuroAIDII) препарати

Introduction. One of the most studied symptoms of brain diseases in neurology is cognitive changes. Cognitive disorders are observed as a result of diffuse damage to the brain as a result of different formations. [2, 14]. Cognitive impairment occurs in 3-20% of people over the age of 65, leading to dementia. Mild cognitive impairment is observed in 40% to 80% of elderly people [11, 15]. In patients with cognitive disorders, memory, cognition- gnosis, speech, daily activity- praxis and intellect. Nowadays, the increase in the age of old age, the many injuries that can occur in the elderly and their effective treatment are medical assistance for neurologists and other specialists [3]. Chronic cerebral ischemia (chronic cerebral ischemia, or dyscirculatory encephalopathy) is one of the most common diagnoses in Russian neurology. This condition is defined as a chronic progressive non-stroke-related vascular lesion of the brain, which is manifested mainly by cognitive impairment. In the International Classification of Diseases of the 10th revision, chronic cerebral ischemia is included in the section "other cerebrovascular diseases" [5, 9]. However, in modern foreign literature, the terms "dyscirculatory encephalopathy" and "chronic cerebral ischemia" are not used, but vascular cognitive impairment (vascular cognitive impairment), which are similar in pathogenesis and clinical manifestations, are distinguished. In 1994, V.C. Hachinski proposed for the first time to use TFR to denote the deterioration of cognitive functions due to cerebrovascular disorders [1, 8, 10-13]. This concept combines both vascular dementia and less severe cognitive impairment of vascular etiology. Among the causes of TFR are various diseases of the cardiovascular system, which lead to cancer or chronic insufficiency of blood supply to the brain. In the vast majority of cases, vascular cerebral insufficiency develops in elderly people with cardiovascular diseases.

Due to the anatomical and physiological features of cerebral circulation, brain lesions in TFR appear earlier and are more often localized in the subcortical basal ganglia and deep sections of the cerebral white matter. At the same time, clinical symptoms are caused not so much by direct ischemic damage as by the disconnection of a number of cerebral structures, mainly the frontal parts of the brain and subcortical structures (the "phenomenon of disconnection"). The most important role in the pathogenesis of neurological disorders and CD in this case is played by a violation of the fronto-striato-pallido-thalamic connections. We are talking about the so-called closed frontal-subcortical circles connecting separate sections of the frontal lobe cortex and subcortical cerebral structures. To date, five frontal-subcortical circles have been described, three of which (dorsolateral prefrontal, lateral orbitofrontal, anterior frontal) are closely related to the provision of cognitive activity. The defeat of each of the links in these vicious circles leads to externally similar cognitive, motor, emotional and behavioral disorders. In this case, during clinical and even neuropsychological examination, it is not always possible to accurately determine the lesion of the brain, often minimal in volume, but leading to significant disorders of mental activity. The symptoms of damage to the above circles may be not only cognitive impairment (slowness of cognitive activity (bradyphrenia), decreased fluency of speech, memory disorders such as reproduction insufficiency, fluctuations in concentration (fluctuations)), but also non-cognitive neuropsychiatric disorders (depression, lability of affect, apathy and other emotional disorders), sleep disorders, as well as motor disorders

in the form of hypokinesia and gait disorders such as frontal dysbasia. It is believed that frontal lobe CR of varying severity can serve as one of the most reliable, objective and early criteria for the presence and severity of vascular brain damage [14-16].

Purpose of the study: Analysis of the effectiveness of treatment of patients with cognitive changes in chronic cerebral blood disorders diseases

Materials and methods of research. To clarify the use of the drug MLC601 (NeuroAIDII) in patients with cognitive impairment. A total of 46 patients who complained of poor memory, rapid fatigue and sleep disturbances participated in our follow-up. Their age was 65-85 years.

Results of the study. All clinical-laboratory, MRI and clinical-neurological tests were performed on all of them Patients were divided into two identical groups: the main group consisted of 23 patients, to whom we recommended NeuroAID II from neurotropic drugs for complex treatment; the second group of our patients consisted of 23 people, and they were given traditional treatment procedures.

In all our patients, the memory loss was 88%, and the loss of large amounts of information was 86%. It was observed in all patients who quickly got tired and had the ability to work. Sleep disturbance was observed in 70% of patients, and changes in the emotional sphere were observed in 65% of patients. For many years, folk medicine has been used to treat the pain of patients using medicinal products made from plants, and even in our modern medicine, medicinal preparations made from plants are used on a large scale in the treatment of diseases.

MLC601 is a medical product, herbal and non-herbal extract capsule drug preparation. MLC601 is included in the group of drugs with neuroprotective and neuroplastic effects [5, 16]. After the treatment, all of our main group of patients had headache, fatigue and weakness. In the second group of patients, the memory loss was 74%, and the reception of a large amount of information was 76%. Sleep disturbance was observed in 45% of patients, change in the emotional sphere was observed in 36% of patients. After treatment, the main (first) group of our patients had a memory decline of 66%, and a large amount of information intake decline was 68%. Sleep disturbance was observed in 20% of patients, change in the emotional sphere was observed in 25% of patients.

Six patients in the main group received NeuroAID II for a month, and their clinical neurological and quality-of-life changes were significantly lower compared to patients who received up to three months.

According to the MMSE test, the second group of patients showed a significant decrease in recall of 10 words before treatment, their average scores were 5.85±0.15 and 24.69±0.36 points. The post-treatment index was 7.8±0.11 and 25.48±0.30 points.

According to the MMSE test, our first group of patients showed a significant decrease in recall of 10 words before treatment, their average score was 5.85±0.15 and 24.69±0.36 points. After treatment, the index increased significantly, that is, it was 7.8±0.11 and 27.59±0.30 points.

Conclusions

1. Natural drug - MLC601 in patients with cognitive changes, when we went to a clinical study, it was confirmed that the clinical-neurological dynamics had high efficiency for 3 months.

2. No side effects were observed in our patients during the use of MLC601.

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